

Allelism between blast (BI) resistance genes *Pi-4a(t)* and *Pi-ta*

T. Inulhai, Faculty of Agriculture, Hokkaido University, Sapporo 060, Japan; R. Nelson, S. Sarlarung, and R. S. Zeigler, IRRI

Twenty-two near-isogenic lines (NILs) carrying single genes for complete resistance to BI were previously developed at IRRI. The recurrent parent was the highly susceptible indica cultivar CO 39. The donor parents were the resistant indica cultivars Tetep and 5173 and japonica cultivars Pai-kan-tao and LAC23. NILs were divided into six groups based on their reaction patterns to IRRI test isolates. The resistance gene in C101PKT, one of the NILs belonging to group III, was designated *Pi-4a(t)*. We found that *Pi-4a(t)* was identical to the

known BI resistance locus *Pi-ta*. All of the NILs in group III were shown to carry *Pi-ta*.

To compare resistance genes in the NILs with previously described BI resistance loci, we conducted allelism tests between C101PKT and Kiyosawa's differentials (KDs), a set of cultivars carrying 12 known resistance genes. We also conducted allelism tests between NILs belonging to group III and KDs.

Seedlings of parental lines and F₂ plants were grown in a greenhouse and inoculated at the fifth- to sixth-leaf stage by spraying with an aqueous spore suspension of 5 × 10⁴ conidia/ml. The pathogen isolates used for developing the NILs, IK81-3 (101), IK81-25 (102), and 43 (105), were also used in these experiments. Disease reactions were scored about 7 d after inoculation.

Table 2. Reaction pattern of K 1, Pi No. 4, and NILs belonging to group III.^a

Line	Test isolates ^b				
	101	102	103	104	105
Kiyosawa's differentials					
K 1 (<i>Pi-ta</i>)	R	R	S	S	R
Pi No. 4 (<i>Pi-ta</i> ²)	R	R	R	R	R
NILs in group III					
C101PKT [<i>Pi-4a(t)</i>]	R	R	S	S	R
C101TTP-1	R	R	S	S	R
C101TTP-2	R	R	S	S	R
C101TTP-3	R	R	S	S	R
C101TTP-4	R	R	S	S	R
C101TTP-6	R	R	S	S	R
C102TTP	R	R	S	S	R
C105TTP-1	R	R	S	S	R
C105TTP-2L23	R	R	S	S	R
C105TTP-4L6	R	R	S	S	R

^aR = resistant, S = susceptible. ^b101 = IK81-3, 102 = IK81-25, 103 = PO6-6, 104 = PO3-82-51, 105 = 43

None of NILs in group III gave susceptible recombinants in the crosses with K 1 (*Pi-ta*) and Pi No. 4 (*Pi-ta*²) at the F₂ generation (Table 1). These results showed that resistance genes in K 1, Pi No. 4, and the NILs in group III are allelic or closely linked. Both K 1 and Pi No. 4 have resistance genes at the *Pi-ta* locus, and it has been reported that Pai-kan-tao (the donor parent of C101PKT) has *Pi-ta*. The reaction pattern of C101PKT and other NILs in group III to five IRRI test isolates was the same as for that of K 1 (*Pi-ta*) (Table 2). These results indicate that *Pi-4a(t)* was identical to *Pi-ta*, and that all of the NILs in group III have *Pi-ta*. ■

Characterization of weakly virulent bacterial strains associated with rice bacterial blight (BB) or leaf streak (BLS) in southern India

S. S. Gnanamanickam, Center for Advanced Studies in Botany, University of Madras, Madras 600025, India; A. M. Alvarez and A. A. Benedict, Plant Pathology and Microbiology Departments, University of Hawaii, 3190 Maile Way, Honolulu, Hawaii 96822; N. Sakthivel and J. E. Leach, Plant Pathology Department, Kansas State University, Manhattan, Kansas 66506, USA

We classified 70 Indian strains of *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* (*Xoo*) from major rice-growing areas in India

Table 1. Reaction of parental lines and F₂ populations to isolate IK81-3 (101).

Parental line and F ₂ population	Reaction to IK81-3 ^a			Goodness of fit	
	R	S	Total	Ratio	χ ²
CO 39 (S line)	0	19	19		
C101PKT [<i>Pi-4a(t)</i>]	20	0	20		
F ₂ CO 39/C101PKT	91	31	122	3:1	0.01 ns
104PKT (S line)	0	18	18		
K 1 (<i>Pi-ta</i>)	12	0	12		
F ₂ K 1/C104PKT	177	44	221	3:1	3.05 ns
C104PKT (S line)	0	17	17		
Pi No. 4 (<i>Pi-ta</i> ²)	16	0	16		
F ₂ Pi No. 4/C104PKT	143	39	182	3:1	1.24 ns
Crosses with NILs in group III					
F ₂ K 1/					
C101PKT	420	0	420	1:0	
C101TTP-1	408	0	408	1:0	
C101TTP-2	413	0	413	1:0	
C101TTP-3	—	—	—	—	
C101TTP-4	236	0	236	1:0	
C101TTP-6	441	0	441	1:0	
C102TTP ^b	192	0	192	1:0	
C105TTP-1 ^c	201	0	201	1:0	
C105TTP-2L23 ^c	119	0	119	1:0	
C105TTP-4L6 ^c	216	0	216	1:0	
F ₂ Pi No. 4/					
C101PKT	392	0	392	1:0	
C101TTP-1	221	—	221	1:0	
C101TTP-2	201	0	201	1:0	
C101TTP-3	107	0	107	1:0	
C101TTP-4	220	0	220	1:0	
C101TTP-6	214	0	214	1:0	
C102TTP ^b	206	0	206	1:0	
C105TTP-1	220	0	220	1:0	
C105TTP-2L23	179	0	179	1:0	
C105TTP-4L6	—	—	—	—	

R = resistant, S = susceptible. ^aIsolate IK81-25 (102) was inoculated. ^bIsolate 43 (105) was inoculated.